

Performance assessment of advanced materials in architectural envelopes

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Abstract

Along the development of society, many research activities are conducted on the development of novel materials, which are ultimately targeted at improving the quality of life of building users. For each particular development, assessment procedures need to be defined, based on the expected performance of materials, considering its final impact in the building where they are installed.

In this work, a specification and assessment framework is proposed at building, construction system and material scale. The type of information for a proper specification is provided, and a set of test typologies are given for each development scales. Furthermore, the link of this procedure with technology readiness roadmaps is provided.

Finally two case studies of full scale assessments are provided for different products: a novel aerogel material, and an industrialized timber component with hemp-based products.

Keywords: Experimental assessment; Materials; Full scale; Testing; Aerogel; Hemp

1. Introduction

In the initial decades of the 21st century, numerous product and system development initiatives have been deployed in the construction industry. Although very different in their approach there is a clear trend in all these developments towards sustainable construction, where issues such as low embodied energy and high performance to boost operational energy efficiency. All this is promoted by public policies- where nearly zero building energy performance is required at latest in 2020-, and products from original niche markets for early adopters have already been transferred to the mainstream construction market.

Although developments are built over an extensive mass of knowledge and technical standards, still the singularities of the construction sector have limited the complete understanding of the behaviour of architectural systems with novel materials. Buildings are one of the largest product delivered by human beings, but at the same time are most commonly designed and constructed on a one-by-one basis, due to local particularities- geography, building codes, urban planning, user needs,... This approach limits the capacity of building designers and constructors to gain scientific and technical knowledge on architectural systems, as their low repeatability makes it difficult to finance deep research or testing procedures. In this sense, most of technical standards in the construction sector are related to calculation procedures at design level, with testing being reduced to material level, with some exceptions.

However, when novel materials and architectural systems based on these need to be developed, other approaches are needed. This is even more relevant if critical competitive advantages of the product is related to thermal building physics, where issues such as thermal dynamics, and representability of the scale of tests is critical when delivering a reliable performance evaluation.

In this paper, an approach to the experimental roadmap of materials is presented, with upscaling from initial tests at materials laboratory scale, to testing of 1:1 samples of building components with realistic boundary conditions. Also intermediate tests are considered for controlled dynamic 1D testing. However, the authors express that, based on their experience from product development, the critical step in the process is a clear definition of higher level specifications (e.g. at building or system level) that is correctly downsized to all the steps in the design and experimentation chain.

Although very diverse performance assessments need to be performed along the development of materials and systems, this work is focused on variables impacting on the thermal performance of building envelopes. Particular cases will be studied, with focus on thermal insulation on small scale samples of superinsulation materials and full scale assessment of low-carbon hemp based developments.

2. Overall development process

Although this paper focused on the experimental assessment, the critical step in the successful development of materials and systems for the construction sector involves a deep understanding of the performance that needs to be tested, its expected variation ranges, and the influence of the defined performance in the overall performance of a building.

In this sense, performance requirements at building and system level need to be gathered prior to developments at material scale in order to correctly specify the development process, and ultimately guide the assessment procedure.

In figure 1, a flowchart is presented where critical information sources, type of specification and assessment procedures are shown for each level of research.

Figure 1: Specification and assessment flow chart for materials and system developments in the construction sector.

3. Technology readiness

In the correct definition of assessment procedures for innovative materials and systems, a critical step is the definition of the technological status of the technology under research.

While several technological metrics are possible, in Europe, the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale is used [1]. This scale classifies 9 levels as follows:

- TRL 1** – basic principles observed
- TRL 2** – technology concept formulated
- TRL 3** – experimental proof of concept
- TRL 4** – technology validated in lab
- TRL 5** – technology validated in relevant environment
- TRL 6** – technology demonstrated in relevant environment
- TRL 7** – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
- TRL 8** – system complete and qualified
- TRL 9** – actual system proven in operational environment

However, the transition from this scale is not obvious, and the position of a single development may differ depending on the scope of the research. As an example, for research in novel fiber-reinforced profiles for its use in construction, TRL 1-5 are mostly related to research at materials laboratory scale, while for research in novel uses of fiber-reinforced profiles for thermally insulated assemblies [2], already TRL 3-4 would require relevantly larger experimental works such as hotbox systems.

In figure 2, the link between experimental assessment levels and the TRL scale are provided two different levels of technology readiness levels for materials and products/systems in the construction sector.

Figure 2: Levels of assessment for the construction sector, and its link to the TRL scale depending on the scope of research.

The hybridization of technologies, and use of materials in applications different than its original purpose should also be carefully considered- e.g. the use of vacuum insulation in the construction sector, has required of deep understanding of modularity, durability, thermal bridging, moisture transfer and other issues which are not critical in other environments such as refrigeration devices. In this sense, the new application would most possibly not require of all the assessment processes as a fully new development, primarily due to the experience gained in the development of the original product, but would certainly imply a relevant reduction in the TRL scale as shown in figure 3 for a case with phase change materials (PCMs)

Figure 3: Assessment of TRL level of a novel application of an already commercial Phase Change Material

4. Performance to be assessed

In the development process of novel materials, many of its properties need to be defined, such as thermal conductivity to Young's modulus, among others. The obtention of these parameters by experimental means is a challenge in itself for each of the fields of research. For this reason, within this paper, only the determination of thermal performance parameters will be dealt with. Thermal performance is commonly related to two parameters:

- Thermal insulation properties: Thermal conductivity, Thermal resistance,...
- Thermal mass properties: Specific heat, density, effective thermal mass,...

Standardized procedures for the determination of most thermal properties are available from sources such as CEN and ISO, but the applicability of these procedures should be carefully evaluated for each case. Special attention should be paid to developments in which non-linear effects may appear such as PCM materials, and multi-foil reflective insulation materials. In both cases, the performance assessment should be carefully defined, as its performance is highly non-linear, far beyond common assumptions in the construction industry:

- In the case of phase change materials, assessments should be defined in such a way that the hysteresis effects of differing phase-change profiles in the charge and discharge processes are considered. Also realistic boundary conditions should be considered in terms of surface heat transfer -which could be referenced to sources such as [3]- and temperature profiles in buildings- which could be obtained by transient building simulation or data from monitorized buildings.
- In the case of multi-foil insulation materials, these materials base its insulation properties in its capacity to block radiation phenomena in the thin foils which compose the element. For this reason its performance is clearly non-linear, and commonly used temperature gradients in full scale laboratory equipment [4] should be modified to account for temperature profiles in buildings.

In figure 4, a test box for transient analysis of one-dimensional heat transfer in materials can be found. This kind of devices, although not suitable for performance certification processes provide of the required experience for the assessment of dynamic energy performance of systems at early research stages, with materials manufactured through pre-industrial techniques

Figure 4: Assessment of TRL level of a novel application of an already commercial Phase Change Material

5. Particular case 1: Performance assessment of a Hemp-based timber-framed HEMP construction

In this section, a full scale performance demonstration process is outlined. This assessment is part of the HEMPSEC project, where a timber-framed component based on hemp-lime compound, and its manufacturing and certification scheme is developed [5].

The benefits of the solution, offering thermal inertia and regulating internal humidity, combined with the breathable insulation, gives to this solution a competitive performance for a low embedded energy solution. The 0.04W/mK conductivity of the fibres combined with 0.074W/mk of the biocomposite provides a very competitive solution with final U-values close to 0.15W/m2K in a 300mm wall section.

Figure 5: Left: Scheme of the main elements composing the system; right: 9m² test sample as installed in the Kubik by TecNALIA test facility.

When defining the experimental campaign for such a system, the main target was set at assessing not only thermal insulation capacity, but also thermal and moisture buffering. The Kubik by TecNALIA test facility [6-7] was selected as it allowed for the definition of the test at full scale- external view of the installed prototype is shown in figure 5-, with adequate control of internal and external boundary conditions.

This facility is located near Bilbao in Spain, and allows for the erection of tailor-made experiments in building envelopes, HVAC and building management systems. For the HEMPSEC project, a portion of the East façade was adapted on the second floor of the building.

The main characteristics to be assessed were defined as follows:

- Thermal insulation capacity
- Presence of thermal bridges
- Thermal buffering capacity
- Moisture buffering capacity

With these parameters as a guide, the test set-up was constructed with three prefabricated elements, in such a way that not only thermal bridges due to the wood frame within one prefabricated component, but also those in horizontal and vertical junctions were introduced in the experiments. The assessment of thermal bridges is made by means of thermal imaging, and also the positioning of temperature and heat flux sensors in the area of influence of these elements.

Thermal insulation, and thermal and moisture buffering capacity are assessed by localized measurements in 4 different measurement axes. The use of several measurement axes is used not only to introduce redundancy in the experiment, but also to provide an indicator of the variability of the assessed parameter.

In each axis temperature and relative humidity sensors are introduced in the experiment. These sensors are located in internal and external surfaces, and also within the prefabricated wall at regular intervals.

The need of assessment of thermal buffering capacity implies also that boundary conditions need to be dynamic. Outdoor conditions are inherently dynamic, and several indoor boundary conditions have been defined along the test campaign with different steady-stated and dynamic oscillation periods in order to correctly solicit the test sample for a proper latter data analysis.

The test was installed in the Kubik by TecNALIA test facility at the end of and is still being monitored.

6. Particular case 2: Performance assessment of a novel aerogel material

In the last years there is an increasing interest in the development of highly insulating materials for the construction industry. In this field of research, aerogels have proven thermal conductivity values in the range 0.01-0.02W/mK, and

are already applied in the construction sector, although only in small amounts due to its high cost. The cost of insulation materials is highly related to the manufacturing process, and the AEROCOINS project [8] targeted at the development of novel aerogel materials by means of ambient drying processes, which would result in a relevantly lower final cost of the aerogel.

Within the project, new aerogels were developed, and upscale to pre-industrial manufacturing processes. Along the development, many experimental assessments were performed at laboratory scale, including hot-wire, guarded hot plate and heat flux measurements on small scale samples.

On the escalation process towards the final market goal, a full scale test was defined at the Kubik by TecNALIA test facility, targeted not only on the thermal performance but also on constructability, and adaptability of the material to architectural junctions, etc.

In this case, the main thermal behavior to be assessed was the insulation properties of the material, at full scale. This was found relevant as previous experiences were all at laboratory scale, and this test would evaluate the impact of transport, and workmanship in the final insulation level of the façade construction.

For this purpose, a pre-existing portion of a prefabricated concrete wall was used, and aerogel was installed on its internal side on a dry construction system with plasterboard as internal lining. Again several measurement axes were installed for redundancy, and the measurement campaign was based on the reference standard for on-site measurement of thermal transmittance [9]. In figure 6, the sensor layout for each of the 4 measurement axes in the AEROCOINS aerogel is presented.

Figure 6: Left: Sensor layout of one measurement axis in the AEROCOINS project; right: Internal view of the test cell.

The test campaign was conducted over the winter and spring of the 2014-2015 season, and steady parameters were achieved, far beyond the requirements in [7], as the measurement campaign was substantially longer and more instrumented. In figure 7, the convergence of the solution is shown, with minor differences among all 4 axes in the plot. After the decomposition of the overall thermal resistance, it was concluded that the thermal conductivity of the aerogel material was in the range 0.015-0.017 W/mK. This result was found coherent with previous measurements at laboratory scale.

Figure 7: Cumulated coupling coefficient of internal insulation systems with AEROCOINS aerogels (base wall excluded from this calculation), in 4 different measurement axes, within the period 2014/11 to 2015/04.

7. Summary and Conclusions

Within the research in novel materials for the construction industry, the assessment of energy-related performance characteristics takes a relevant role. In this role, although normative references and test procedures are available for some cases, a clear specification of the performance to be addressed is necessary. In this process, it is found critical that the performance is framed in the context of the final energy performance at building scale.

The performance assessment needs to be performed in steps, along with the increase in the technology readiness of the material or system which is developed. In cases of hybridation or alternative use of a material, a critical review of present information and its applicability is needed in order to correctly re-position the system into a technology readiness scale for its particular final use.

On the particular definition of performance assessment needs it is found that these needs are clearly diverse, and that these should be defined case by case, based on the competitive advantages of each material being developed. In this approach, two case studies are provided, where the definition of the test environment and results are provided.

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8. References

- [1] TRL Scale, http://www.innovationseeds.eu/Virtual_Library/Knowledge/TLR_Scale.kl (2015/07/02)
- [2] R. Garay Martinez, New challenges on building systems with superinsulation materials, 1st Workshop on High Performance Thermal Insulation (HPI) 2013, ZAE Bayern, Wurzburg; 2013
- [3] ISO 6946:2007, Building components and building elements -- Thermal resistance and thermal transmittance -- Calculation method
- [4] ISO 8990:1994, Thermal insulation -- Determination of steady-state thermal transmission properties -- Calibrated and guarded hot box
- [5] HEMPSEC, pre-fabricated, pre-dried panelised system of hemp-lime construction, <http://www.bath.ac.uk/ace/research/cicm/hempsec/> (2015/07/02)
- [6] KUBIK by Tecnia, Experimental Infrastructure for the Configuration of Zero Energy Buildings, http://www.tecnalia.com/images/stories/construccion-sostenible/infraestructuras-equipamiento/TECNALIA_kubik_eng_2.pdf (2015/07/02)
- [7] R. Garay Martinez, et Al. Energy efficiency achievements in 5 years through experimental research in KUBIK, 6th International Building Physics Conference, 2015. To be published in Energy Procedia.
- [8] AEROCOINS, Aerogel-Based Composite/Hybrid Nanomaterials for Cost-Effective Building Super-Insulation Systems, <http://www.aerocoins.eu/> (2015/07/02)
- [9] ISO 9869-1:2014, Thermal insulation -- Building elements -- In-situ measurement of thermal resistance and thermal transmittance -- Part 1: Heat flow meter method